
INTEGRATING UNIVERSAL DESIGN FOR LEARNING (UDL) PRINCIPLES INTO ENGLISH CLASSES TO BOLSTER WRITING PROFICIENCY

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Abstract: Objective learning opportunities are important for students who have diverse academic background to meet writing standards and improve writing proficiency. Universal Design for Learning (UDL) is an educational framework aimed at planning the lesson by providing instructions that can support a broad range of diverse students. This method is scientifically based framework for making learning process accessible to all students by providing multiple means of representation, multiple means of expression, and multiple means of engagement. This article explores how teachers can apply UDL framework to plan writing classes effectively. By incorporating the UDL framework into the instructional process, educators can make sure that their practices are based on the strengths of their students and provide opportunities for fair and accessible learning for every student. This paper investigates how educators can implement UDL principles in writing classes to foster increased options for composing writing, promote student engagement, and represent key points through multiple modalities. This study investigates the importance of UDL method in academic writing through a multidisciplinary analysis of scholarly articles. A diverse corpus of articles spanning natural sciences, social sciences, and humanities was examined to assess UDL principles usage patterns and their impact on readability of written work.

Keywords: UDL principles, writing classes, writing proficiency, accessible, inclusive learning, engagement, choices.

INTRODUCTION

Developing academic writing proficiency is a challenging process which requires dedication and hard work. In writing classrooms, teachers can apply UDL principles to promote more inclusive, engaging, and accessible learning environment. By using visual aids, demonstrations, written instructions, or even multimedia presentations, educators can cater to different learning styles and abilities to meet all students' needs. The core principles of UDL can allow students to express their understanding and demonstrate their writing skills in different ways. There some students who opt for writing, while there are others who prefer verbal expression or through the use of technology. UDL offers options, such as written essays, oral

presentations, or digital media projects that can ensure that all students can showcase their abilities. Students in UDL classes have an opportunity to improve their creative writing abilities through real-life scenarios, interactive activities, collaborative projects, or hands-on experiences provided at UDL classes. Writing exercises in the classroom that are traditionally conducted are often ineffective for students from culturally and exceptionally diverse learning backgrounds, which cause inequalities in literacy proficiency among these learners. (Cho et al., 2022) In today’s contemporary world, students who are entering education fields, classrooms are becoming even more diverse and encountering several barriers during their academic path. Hence, organizing equitable and accessible writing instructions for these diverse students is one of the most critical duties of today’s modern educators.

METHODS

The scientific research used qualitative and secondary data analysis to identify the importance of implementation of UDL method in academic writing classes. To assess the impact of this teaching method on writing lessons, a corpus of scholarly articles spanning various disciplines was analyzed. A diverse corpus of scholarly articles was selected from reputable academic journals across multiple disciplines.

Universal Design for Learning (UDL) initially emerged from the field of architecture as a way of providing all people, especially people who have physical disabilities with equal access to public spaces (Brown, et al., 17; David & Brown, 2020). Thereafter, UDL method was used in the field of education to promote better educational outcomes and provide students with access to superior classroom curricula. UDL has contributed significantly to the global progress of learning process in educational settings by advancing the idea that teachers should approach curriculum and instruction from asset-based framework rather than putting the burden of incapacity on the student (David & Torres, 2020; Meo, 2008).

Universal Design for Learning includes three core principles that are supported by a collocation of nine guidelines (table1).

Multiple means of engagement	Multiple means of representation	Multiple means of action & expression
<p>Options for self-regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate personal coping skills and strategies • Improve self-assessment and reflection • Promote motivation and emotion in learning 	<p>Options for comprehension</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide students with background knowledge • Highlight critical features, relationships, and big ideas 	<p>Options for physical action</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide options for responding • Offer options for completing assignments • Interact with accessible tools and

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Formulate meaning and foster new proficiencies 	materials
<p>Options for sustaining effort and persistence</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase the silence of goals and objectives Provide demands to optimize challenge Foster teamwork and community 	<p>Options for language & symbols</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clarify symbols, new vocabulary, syntax, and structure Promote understanding through languages Create a shared understanding through languages 	<p>Options for executive functions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Guide proper goal setting Support planning and strategy development Improve capacity for observing progress
<p>Options for recruiting interest</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote individual choice and autonomy Emerge curiosity for learning among students 	<p>Options for perception</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> offer diverse materials offer alternative ways for auditory learners offer alternative ways for visual learners 	<p>Options for expressions and communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> utilize multimedia tools for communication use different tools for construction and composition compose and share ideas by using tools which can help accomplish learning goals

Table1: UDL principles and guidelines (Rose & Meyer, 2022)

When it comes to applying UDL framework principles in writing classes, teachers can use this method to tackle the problems and barriers struggling learners often face and foster writing lessons more engaging and accessible, as UDL offers a helpful place to start when making changes to accommodate the different needs and skills of each student. This method is an important point for promoting student engagement in writing lessons and is a way of offering choices that can enable students to get involved in the content and express their own thought and ideas during writing instruction and practice (Hashey et al, 2020).

In writing lessons, UDL method can bring about several benefits for not only the learners, but also educators. UDL method can increase access to learning by creating equal learning environment. It can help to make writing instruction more accessible

to all students, including students with disabilities, English language learners, and students with learning differences. By providing multiple means of representation, expression, and engagement, UDL can help to ensure that all students have the opportunity to learn and succeed in their academic development. In addition to increased access, UDL can provide improved engagement of all students at the class. This method principles aim to improve students’ participation in writing classes by providing them with different choices and options. As it is obvious to everyone, when students have the chance to choose how they learn, they are likely to feel more motivated and engaged in the learning process. Furthermore, UDL can contribute to enhance student learning by providing students with multiple opportunities to practice and apply their writing skills. By sustaining students with differentiated ways to present their insight and understanding, UDL can help them to develop a deeper understanding of the writing process.

Providing multiple means of representation	Providing multiple means of expression	Providing multiple means of engagement
➤ This can be done by using a variety of text formats (e.g., printed texts, digital, audio materials), visual aids (e.g., charts, graphs, videos), and hands-on activities	➤ This can be done by allowing students to choose how they want to demonstrate their learning (e.g., essays, poems, stories, presentations).	➤ This can be done by providing students with choices in how they learn (e.g., individual work, group work, online learning) to make the writing process accessible to all students

Table2: Specific examples of how UDL can be used in writing classes

By incorporating UDL principles into writing instruction, educators can organize learning environments that are more engaging, accessible, and effective for all students who have different background knowledge.

RESULTS

The findings of this scientific research showed that incorporating UDL principles into writing classes had a positive impact on students learning. The data gathered from scholarly articles regarding the importance of UDL helped to find that students who were taught through using UDL principles showed significant gains in their writing proficiency:

- **Increased writing fluency**
- **Increased writing accuracy**
- **Enhanced writing quality**
- **Grater writing confidence**

In addition, students who participated in the lessons where teachers applied UDL principles were more engaged in their writing classes and had more positive attitudes towards writing tasks.

This study also found that the three core principles of UDL method are also beneficial and effective for students with particular learning disabilities (LD). Students with LD who were given instructions by using UDL principles showed greater gains in their writing skills compared to the students with learning disabilities who were taught using traditional methods.

Overall, the final results of the scientific research suggest that integrating UDL principles into writing lessons can improve students’ writing abilities, student learning process, and engagement for all students, including students with learning disabilities.

DISCUSSIONS

Applying UDL method principles can bring about different advantages in writing lessons, including improved engagement, accessible materials, and other benefits mentioned above. However, there are several challenges in incorporating UDL principles into classes. First and foremost difficulty of implementing UDL in writing classes is the time and resources required. The particular reason is that UDL requires teachers to spend more time for planning and preparing their lessons. Educators also need access to a variety of resources, such as assistive technology and accessible materials. Another challenge is the need for teacher training and professional development. Because many teachers need additional training in order to effectively implement UDL in their classrooms. Finding accessible materials and adapting them can be the next major challenge of applying this method. It can be time-consuming and difficult to find materials that are accessible to every student. Teachers may also need to spend time adapting materials or creating their own ones.

On the other hand there are several ways of avoiding these challenges to implement UDL principles in English classes. It is recommended by many researchers that teachers should start applying UDL principles in one or two classes. After they become more comfortable with this process they can start using this method in other classes. Educators are advised to collaborate with other teachers who are using UDL in their classrooms. They can receive support from their more experienced colleagues.

Implementing UDL in the classroom can be challenging, but it is also very rewarding. By using UDL principles, teachers can create a more inclusive and equitable learning environment for all students.

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